

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of incentives, workload, supervision and work environment on nurse performance at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024

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Abstract

Background: Nurses as part of the health workforce in hospitals work in a physical environment working in an environment where disease transmission occurs. Meanwhile, non-physically, nurses work to provide services to sick individuals who require special attention. Therefore, nurses really need a comfortable environment in order to provide optimal health services. This research aims to determine the influence of incentives, workload, supervision and work environment on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024.

Method: The type of research used is analytical research which is observational using a cross sectional research design with univariate tests, bivariate and multivariate tests. The population in this study were all nurses in the Inpatient Room at RSU Bahteramas, Southeast Sulawesi Province with a sampling technique using proportional random sampling of 129 people. Data analysis used the chi-square test and logistic regression.

Results: Research shows that there is an influence of workload on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital ($0.029 < 0.05$), there is a significant influence between supervision on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital ($0.046 < 0.05$), there is a significant influence between the work environment and the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital ($0.011 < 0.05$), and there was no significant influence between incentives on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital ($0.268 > 0.05$). The workload variable is the variable that most influences performance with an Exp(B) result of 2,490.

Keywords: Nurse Performance Incentives; Workload; Monitoring Work Attitudes.

1. Introduction

Presidential Regulation Number 72 of 2012 concerning the National Health System states that the implementation of health efforts in the context of health development requires health human resources that are sufficient in number, type and quality and are proportioned fairly and evenly. Health human resources include groups of health workers, consisting of medical personnel, pharmaceutical personnel, nursing and midwifery personnel, public health personnel, environmental health personnel, nutrition personnel, physical therapy personnel, medical technical personnel, and other health workers who do not meet the requirements (1).

UU no. 36 of 2009 concerning health, article 23 states that health workers have the authority to provide health services in accordance with their field of expertise. Furthermore, article 24 explains that health workers must comply with service standards. In this case, health services are health efforts organized to create the highest possible level of health for individuals or society (2).

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One of the determining factors for the success of health services in hospitals is health services, 80% of health services are provided by nurses in every country and in Indonesia as many as 40% of health service providers are nurses. Nursing personnel make a significant contribution to the services provided by hospitals, because they provide constant and continuous service to customers, namely patients and their families, 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. Therefore, health personnel services determine quality and shape the image of the hospital (3).

High nurse workload can result in a decrease in nurse performance and lack or poor communication between patients and nurses, affecting the patient's condition, resulting in poor quality of nursing services (4). High nursing workload can have a significant impact on the care of patients and their families, and can reduce patient satisfaction with care (5). According to Gilles (2009), poor performance causes patient and family satisfaction which can have an impact on the quality of hospital services. One of the factors that influences the risk of decreased performance is workload. The workload can increase if the number of nurses is not commensurate with the level of patient service (6).

The work environment in hospitals has a significant influence on the performance and job satisfaction of medical and non-medical personnel. The work environment in hospitals can be divided into two types, namely physical and non-physical. The physical environment includes the facilities and infrastructure available in the hospital, such as rooms, medical equipment and other supporting facilities. Meanwhile, the non-physical environment includes factors such as policies, organizational culture, and relationships between employees. Several studies show that a conducive work environment can improve the performance and job satisfaction of medical and non-medical personnel in hospitals. Therefore, it is important for hospitals to create a good and conducive work environment for employees in order to improve their performance and job satisfaction (7).

Providing compensation for services to workers at the agency is one form of appreciation from the hospital. Providing incentives will influence employee behavior in their work, so hospitals need to pay attention to the logical consequences for employees in order to improve work performance. Incentives are a form of appreciation or reward to employees in the form of money that is not fixed or at any time based on the performance and achievements that have been achieved with the aim of increasing employee motivation and work productivity (8).

Based on data obtained from the Bahteramas Hospital Medical Records, data on inpatient visits in 2020 was 10,120 patients, in 2021 there were 11,530 patients, and in 2022 there were 15,768 patients. Outpatient visits in 2020 were 90,277 patients, in 2021 there were 91,201 patients, and in 2022 there were 119,796 patients.

Based on data on the achievement of minimum service standards at RSU Bahteramas in 2022, it shows that several programs have not achieved the specified Minimum Service Standards (SPM), namely outpatient satisfaction (80.95%) from the standard $\geq 90\%$, inpatient satisfaction 79.85 % of standard $\geq 90\%$ and completeness of filling in medical records 24 hours after completion of service 85% of standard $\geq 100\%$. Thus, based on data which shows that at Bahteramas RSU there are still several SPMs such as outpatient satisfaction, inpatient satisfaction and completeness of filling in medical records 24 hours after completion of services which are not in accordance with standards, meaning that employee performance has not been carried out optimally in accordance with predetermined standards. This is because providing information about clarity of procedures and clarity of costs, as well as ways of communicating still need attention, the quality of facilities and infrastructure is low.

Based on the background description above, pThis is the basis for researchers to conduct research with the title ""The influence of incentives, workload, supervision and work environment on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024."

2. Materials and Methods

This type of research is observational analytical research with a cross sectional research design using univariate tests, bivariate and multivariate tests. The population in this study were all 196 nurses in the Inpatient Room at Bahteramas RSU, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The sample in this study was part of the total population at RSU Bahteramas of 129 people. The sampling technique used is proportional random sampling, which is a sampling technique in which all members have the same opportunity to be sampled according to the proportion of the population. The data used are primary and secondary data. The instruments in this research used laptops, cellphones, books, pens to record the required data.

The criteria used in determining the sample in this study include inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria are a number of specific criteria that must be present or fulfilled by research subjects. Exclusion criteria are characteristics that should not be present in respondents because they can be confounding in the research.

2.1. Inclusion Criteria

- Nurse in the inpatient room at RSU Bahteramas.
- Nurses whose work period is more than 1 year
- Willing to be a respondent

2.2. Exclusion Criteria

- Nurse on leave

3. Result and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the proportion of respondents who rated nurse performance in the poor category was 62 people (48.1%) and 67 people in the good category (51.9%). The proportion of respondents who rated incentives in the poor category was 58 people (45.0%) and 71 people in the sufficient category (55.0%). The proportion of respondents who assessed their workload in the light workload category was 79 people (61.2%) and 50 people in the heavy workload category (38.8%). The proportion of respondents who rated supervision in the poor category was 59 people (45.7%) and 70 people in the good category (54.3%). The proportion of respondents who rated the work environment in the uncomfortable category was 62 people (48.1%) and 67 people in the comfortable category (51.9%).

Table 1 Univariate Analysis The Influence of Incentives, Workload, Supervision and Work Environment on Nurse Performance at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024

Variable	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Nurse Performance		
Not good	62	48.1
Good	67	51.9
Total	129	100
Incentive		
Not enough	58	45.0
Enough	71	55.0
Total	129	100
Workload		
Light workload	79	61.2
Heavy workload	50	38.8
Total	129	100
Supervision		
Not good	59	45.7
Good	70	54.3
Total	129	100
Work environment		
Uncomfortable	62	48.1
Comfortable	67	51.9
Total	129	100

Table 2 Bivariate Analysis The Influence of Incentives, Workload, Supervision and Work Environment on Nurse Performance at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024

Variable	Nurse Performance				Total		p-value
	Not good		Good				
	N	%	n	%	N	%	
Incentive							
Not enough	31	27.9	27	30.1	67	100	0.268
Enough	31	34.1	40	36.9	62	100	
Total	62	62.0	67	67.0	129	100	
Workload							
Light workload	44	38.0	35	41.0	79	100	0.029
Heavy workload	18	24.0	32	26.0	50	100	
Total	62	62.0	67	67.0	129	100	
Supervision							
Not good	34	28.4	25	30.6	59	100	0.046
Good	28	33.6	42	36.4	70	100	
Total	62	62.0	67	67.0	129	100	
Work environment							
Uncomfortable	37	29.8	25	32.2	62	100	0.011
Comfortable	25	32.2	42	34.8	67	100	
Total	62	62.0	67	67.0	129	100	

Based on table 2, the bivariate analysis shows that the proportion of respondents who had less incentives, with poor nurse performance, was 31 respondents (27.9%) and 27 respondents with good performance (30.1%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had sufficient incentives with poor nursing performance was 31 respondents (34.1%) and 40 respondents with good performance (36.9%). The results of statistical tests using chi-square on the incentive variable obtained a value of $p = 0.268$, where the value of $p > \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is no relationship between incentives and nurse performance.

Based on bivariate analysis, it shows that the proportion of respondents who had a light workload with poor nursing performance was 44 respondents (38.0%) and good performance was 35 respondents (41.0%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a heavy workload with poor nursing performance was 18 respondents (24.0%) and 32 respondents with good performance (26.0%). The results of statistical tests using chi-square on the workload variable obtained a value of $p = 0.029$, where the value of $p < \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between workload and nurse performance.

Table 5.11 Based on bivariate analysis shows that the proportion of respondents who had a light workload with poor nursing performance was 44 respondents (38.0%) and good performance was 35 respondents (41.0%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a heavy workload with poor nursing performance was 18 respondents (24.0%) and 32 respondents with good performance (26.0%). The results of statistical tests using chi-square on the workload variable obtained a value of $p = 0.029$, where the value of $p < \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between workload and nurse performance.

Based on bivariate analysis, it shows that the proportion of respondents who had an uncomfortable work environment with poor nurse performance was 37 respondents (29.8%) and good performance was 25 respondents (32.2%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a comfortable work environment with poor nurse performance was 25 respondents (32.2%) and good performance was 42 respondents (34.8%). The results of statistical tests using chi-square on the work environment variable obtained a value of $p = 0.011$, where the value of $p < \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between the work environment and nurse performance.

Table 3 Logistic Regression Test Results on Variables that Influence Nurse Performance

Sub Variable	Wald	Sig	Exp(B)
Workload	5,402	0.020	2,490
Supervision	3,043	0.081	1,965
Work environment	4,199	0.040	2,178

Based on table 3 in the variable in the equation table above using logistic regression analysis, there are several variables that influence nurse performance, namely workload, supervision and work environment variables. Meanwhile, the variable that has the most influence on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province is the workload variable with a significance value (sig) of 0.020, $p < \alpha$ (0.25) and the odd ratio (OR) = 2.490 is the largest value among other variables.

3.1. The Effect of Incentives on Nurse Performance

Incentives are a form of direct payment that is based on or directly related to performance and profits obtained (9). Employee behavior at work depends on the provision of incentives, whether the hospital needs to pay attention to logical consequences for employees in order to improve work performance. Incentives are a form of appreciation or reward to employees in the form of money that is not fixed over time based on performance and achievements that have been achieved with the aim of increasing employee motivation and work productivity (8).

Based on the results of the research, it shows that the proportion of respondents with poor performance in nurses with poor performance was 40 respondents (32.2%) and with good performance there were 22 respondents (29.8%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had sufficient incentives with poor nurse performance was 22 respondents (29.8%) and good performance was 40 respondents (32.2%).

Based on the results of statistical tests using chi-square on the incentive variable, a value of $p = 0.268$ was obtained, where the value of $p > \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is no relationship between incentives and nurse performance. This is because the incentives given to nurses are given in accordance with the provisions of the hospital which are given in the form of money every month. Incentives given to health workers, especially nurses, who carry out their duties in accordance with what is expected. However, the amount of incentives received by each health worker, especially nurses, is unknown because receiving incentives is also related to employee performance targets (SKP) which are confidential so it is not possible to compare incentives between one hospital and another. We know that providing incentives can increase the work enthusiasm of health workers, especially nurses, and can also provide additional income to meet their daily needs. The existence of proposals such as providing incentives in the form of holiday packages to every nurse who has good performance every 3 months or every 6 months can also increase their work productivity.

In this study, there were respondents who assumed their incentives were sufficient, but there were respondents whose performance was poor, while among respondents who assumed their incentives were insufficient, there were respondents whose performance was good. This can happen because there are several reasons or external factors that can influence this and it could also be because the relationship between superiors and subordinates will influence daily activities.

Based on this description, it is known that incentives are a factor that contributes to employee performance. For this reason, it is necessary for hospitals to pay more attention to the indicators that serve as benchmarks for assessment and to disseminate information thoroughly and comprehensively to all employees to provide incentives so that no more parties feel disadvantaged, meaning that nurses who perform well or poorly are correct. -really obtain proportional rights (incentives).

This finding is in line with research (Suryani, et.al, 2021) which states that the hypothetical results of providing incentives have a calculated t of 0.349 with a t table of 1.978. So t count (0.349) < t table (1.978) it can be concluded that providing incentives has no effect on nurse performance(10).

This finding is in line with research (Ulum, 2021) which states that incentives have no influence on the performance of nurses at Prembun Hospital. This is because the calculated t value is $-1.700 < t$ table 1.979 with a significance of 0.092 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the incentive variable has no influence on nurse performance and H_0 is accepted and (H_1) is rejected. The results of this research show that there is no influence of incentives on the performance of nurses

at Prembun Regional Hospital. This is because incentives are distributed based on length of service, which creates chaos and jealousy between senior and junior nurses.(11).

However, this is different from the findings of (Afhina, et.al, 2020) that the results of testing incentive variables have an influence on the performance of nurses at Pembalah Batung Amuntai Regional Hospital, South Kalimantan. This can be proven by the Sig value. $0.000 < \alpha 0.05$ then it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted because by paying attention to providing incentives fairly and openly, it can maximize the enthusiasm and work productivity of nurses(12).

3.2. The Effect of Workload on Nurse Performance

Workload is the ability of a worker's body to accept work. The workload a person receives must be appropriate and balanced with the physical and psychological abilities of the worker who receives the workload. Physical workload can include heavy work such as lifting, pushing and caring. Meanwhile, psychological workload can be the extent of the level of expertise and work performance that an individual has compared to other individuals. If the workload that must be borne by nurses exceeds their capacity, it will have a negative impact on the nurse's work productivity.

Based on the research results, it shows that the proportion of respondents who have a light workload with poor nursing performance is 44 respondents (38.0%) and there are 35 respondents with good performance (41.0%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a heavy workload with poor nursing performance was 18 respondents (24.0%) and 32 respondents with good performance (26.0%).

Based on the results of statistical tests using chi-square on the workload variable, a value of $p = 0.029$ was obtained, where the value of $p < \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between workload and nurse performance. Based on the logistic regression test, it is known that the Sig. workload is $0.020 < 0.25$ so it can be concluded that there is an influence of workload on the performance of nurses in the inpatient room at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This is because nurses feel they need additional time to complete their work. In this case, it means that nurses understand their duties and the working time they have. Patient visits are carried out by several nurses every 3x a day, where every day they have to meet patients who have different disease histories so that no matter how many patients are handled every day and the tasks they carry out, the nurses are always ready and work optimally by making the most of their time. which exists. The lack of nursing staff is one of the workloads of nurses because the number of patients is always increasing, but in their work nurses are always fully responsible for carrying out patient care until they recover by administering intensive medicines.

Factors that influence a person's workload can be classified into internal factors and external factors. Internal factors such as the condition of the nurse itself means the high ability and hard work of the nurse in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Meanwhile, external factors include an imbalance in the number of nurses and the number of patients, an uncomfortable physical environment, poor interpersonal relationships, demands from the hospital that require nurses to always provide quality nursing care services (13).

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by (Rezeki, et.al, 2023) from the results of hypothesis testing analysis it is known that workload has a significant effect on performance as assessed by a path coefficient of 0.124. The probability value obtained is $0.026 < 0.05$, with a calculated t value of 2.237, and a t table value of 1.96, thus greater than ($2.237 > 1.96$) so that H_0 is rejected (H_a is accepted). This means that the workload has a significant effect on the performance of nurses in the Covid-19 patient treatment room at Dr. RSUD. Pirngadi Medan. This shows that with the increase in workload, the performance of nurses in the Covid-19 patient treatment room at Dr. Regional Hospital. Pirngadi Medan will decrease further, where with the addition of workload that is not in accordance with the nurses' abilities, the nurses will get tired and thus the nurse's performance will decrease further (14).

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by (Septiani, et.al, 2023) which found that more than half of the nurses at RSUD dr. La Palaloi Maros has a high workload (50.8%). The results of this research showed that there was an influence of workload on the performance of nurses at RSUD dr. La Palaloi Maros ($p: 0.000$) where workload is negatively correlated with nurse performance, which means that nurses whose workload is high tend to have low performance and vice versa, nurses whose workload is low tend to have high performance ($r: -0.718 ;$) with strong correlation strength. In this study, nurses were found whose workload was low but their performance was low, and nurses were also found whose workload was high but their performance was high. This shows that workload is not the only factor related to work performance, but can also be influenced by other factors such as workload and work environment (15).

The results of this research are inversely proportional to research conducted by (Yustikasari & Santoso, 2023), it was found that workload had a negative effect on employee performance. Unacceptable, with path coefficients of -0.047048, and a T-statistic value of 0.497661 smaller. from the Z value $a = 0.05$ (5%) = 1.96, then it is not significant (negative)(16).

3.3. The Effect of Supervision on Nurse Performance

According to Royce and Helmi (2016), "supervision is the process of observing the implementation of all organizational activities to ensure that all work being carried out runs according to predetermined plans". Supervision in this research is the nurse's perception of the activities carried out by the head of the room and other management to develop the nurse's abilities, facilitate and guide.

Based on the research results, it shows that the proportion of respondents who had poor supervision with poor nursing performance was 34 respondents (28.4%) and good performance was 25 respondents (30.6%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had good supervision with poor nursing performance was 28 respondents (33.6%) and good performance was 42 respondents (36.4%).

Based on the results of statistical tests using chi-square on the supervision variable, a value of $p = 0.046$ was obtained, where the value of $p < \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between supervision and nurse performance. Based on the logistic regression test, it is known that the Sig. supervision was $0.081 < 0.25$ so it can be concluded that there is an influence of supervision on the performance of nurses in the inpatient room at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This could be because the head of the room has full voting rights in providing assessments to its members both in providing incentives, promotions and recommendations for nursing career development.

The monitoring system in the Bahteramas RSU inpatient room has been implemented, although according to the nurse it is not yet optimal because there are several leadership policies, especially supervision which has decreased slightly because supervision is only borne by the head of the room, while the head of the room himself is still very overwhelmed if he has to spend his time 7x24 hours. to monitor the performance of its members. Supervision variables are one way of monitoring the implementation of programs and tasks that have been given to health workers at RSU Bahteramas, especially nurses, which are binding and administrative in nature so that the performance of health workers in the process of carrying out work, especially in terms of service to patients, both outpatient and inpatient, can run smoothly. in accordance with the specified hospital SOP. Creating good and positive work results such as quality service to people who seek treatment at RSU Bahteramas so that the reflection of the agency's work in the eyes of the local community will be good. There is a contribution from the head of the room by controlling the performance of nurses and providing direction to nurses who have just worked or who have been working for a long time regarding things that need to be considered in treating patients.

This finding is in line with research (Wijaya et.al, 2023) which found that the monitoring variable (X1) obtained a calculation result of 0.001, where this result is smaller than the significance level, namely 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$) and it can be seen that t -calculated monitoring variables are greater than the t-table, namely ($5.757 > 2.002$). So partially the supervision variable (X1) has a significant effect on employee performance(17).

These findings are in line with research (Ahmad Averus & Andi Pitono, 2018) obtained the results of the regression analysis of variance obtained the F value table is $F [0.05:2:43] = 3.215$. Because of the F value count $> F$ table , so it can be interpreted that together supervision sub-variable (X) can influence employee performance variable (Z). Supervision sub variables in this research is direct supervision (X) and indirect supervision (X). From the results analysis and calculation that the test results are significant, because from the results of the path coefficient test Obtained objective information, that the path coefficient of supervision of employee performance, statistically is t count = 4,050 and 2,759 $> t$ table = 2.018 is meaningful The calculated t value $> t$ table, so it can be concluded secondly significant path(18).

3.4. The Influence of the Work Environment on Nurse Performance

The work environment is the environment where employees carry out their daily duties and work. One of the health workers in a hospital, such as a nurse, works in an environment where disease transmission occurs and nurses must provide health services for sick individuals who require special attention. Therefore, nurses need a comfortable work environment to provide optimal medical services (19).

The work environment is everything that exists and has an influence on the performance of nurses to carry out their work with optimal work results. When nurses feel motivated to carry out their work, the services provided by nurses will improve in a good direction. In order to increase motivation for nurses' performance in a hospital environment,

measurements can be made using work performance, for example by providing rewards for nurses who have carried out their work seriously.(3).

Based on the research results, it shows that the proportion of respondents who had an uncomfortable work environment with poor nurse performance was 37 respondents (29.8%) and 25 respondents had good performance (32.2%). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who had a comfortable work environment with poor nursing performance was 25 respondents (32.2%) and 42 respondents (34.8%) had good performance.

Based on the results of statistical tests using chi-square on the work environment variable, the value of $p = 0.011$ was obtained, where the value of $p < \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between the work environment and nurse performance. Based on the logistic regression test, it is known that the Sig. work environment is $0.040 < 0.25$ so it can be concluded that there is an influence of the work environment on the performance of nurses in the inpatient room at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This is because the lighting (sun and lamp) in the nurse's work room is quite comfortable, the use of good wall colors so that you can work more carefully, but the air exchange (temperature) is still lacking so that when you work you can't concentrate because of the heat in the room. as well as narrow spatial planning due to the large number of patient files. A comfortable work environment can increase nurses' motivation to work and vice versa, an uncomfortable work environment can affect nurses' performance. A good work environment can also start from actively communicating with other nurses or health workers in the room regarding actions that have been and will be taken in the future for inpatients. The existence of solidarity between nurses and nurses, nurses and doctors can increase enthusiasm in improving performance.

This finding is in line with research (Suherman et.al, 2023) which showed that hypothesis testing for work environment variables showed a t value of 3.864. With sample size $(n)=35$ and $k=3$, the table value is 1.693. Based on the criteria, the calculated t is greater than the table ($3,864 > 1.693$), and using a significance level where the sig value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$). Thus H_0 is rejected, but with the criteria H_1 is accepted. It can be concluded that partially the work environment variables have a significant effect on nurse performance(20).

This finding is in line with research (Nanda Meisya Putri et.al 2023) which obtained a p-value of 0.044. With a p value < 0.05 , it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted.

4. Conclusion

There is an influence of workload, supervision and work environment on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024 with the results of the chi-square statistical test where the p value $< \alpha$ (0.05). Meanwhile, there is no influence of incentives on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2024 with the results of the chi-square statistical test where the p value is $> \alpha$ (0.05). The workload variable is the most influential variable among the other variables.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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